

Practices of intercultural competence teaching: an autobiographical study at aviation English classroom

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 10, 2023

Revised Apr 19, 2024

Accepted May 18, 2024

Keywords:

Autobiographical study
Aviation English
English specific purpose
Instructional model
Intercultural competence

ABSTRACT

The practice of intercultural teaching seems to be commonly applied but not in aviation English class. This might be difficult in conceptualizing intercultural competence instructional model (ICCIM) due to the mandatory adaptation to aviation English materials. This autobiographical study aimed to describe how the researcher conducted intercultural competence (ICC) teaching in aviation English class along with the depiction of students' reflective constructs. This study was undertaken in Politeknik Penerbangan Surabaya as one of state aviation schools under agency of human resource development on transportation. The researcher found that the ICCIM could be implemented in aviation English class with some challenges. Another finding showed that the students were interested in learning ICC materials. This autobiographical study implies that there needs further research in examining ICCIM in aviation English class with wider cultural exposures and practices to give aviation students wider cultural perspectives before they work in the field of aviation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Language learners are often encountered with frequent potholes in regard to cultural differences. It should be highlighted that language cannot be separated from the presence of multicultural understanding [1]–[4]. Before we relate the intercultural competence (ICC) to English specific purpose (ESP), let us recall the method of language learning applied in the classroom in early education. Language educators who reside in non-English speaking countries are substantially not obliged to comprehend intercultural communicative competence. The majority of public schools in Indonesia, particularly, are not familiar with cross-cultural understanding within English class, except in higher education. In addition, ESP learning requires broad understanding of interculturality where it is feasible for language learners to grasp the notion of differences between foreign cultures and their own. Teaching intercultural concepts is therefore of paramount importance for ESP classroom, given that student will not focus on linguistic competence solely, i.e., grammatical rules and knowledge, but also social knowledge [5], [6].

It has been a long handicap for language educators to involve intercultural communication during language learning process [7]–[9]. English language test (ELT) has always been a showcase for teachers to demonstrate concept of intercultural understanding, yet once again, practically it does not seem conspicuous. Research by Sercu *et al.* [10] pinpoints the absence of the relationship between teachers' perception of ICC integration and their teaching activities, which led to the conclusion that their willingness to teach English as

a foreign language (EFL) is not necessarily interpreted as more culture teaching practices, in terms of frequency. The adherence to localized English books rather than international books is likely to occur in large scale in non-English speaking countries. For some reasons, ICC is deemed necessary to boost the effectiveness of cross-cultural communication [7]. It is crucial for teachers to acquire high perceptions of ICC by amplify their competence through watching English movies, reading many books, or interacting with native speakers. Hence, they consider ICC is important to raise awareness for successful cross-cultural communication and to clarify the social and cultural norms of the language learned [11].

Intercultural teaching can be tricky in practical situation. Teachers are first obliged to primarily focus on students' ability enhancement of their own identity [12], [13] equalize the perspectives of cultural differences, and develop decent attitudes towards other cultures. Comparative analysis could be employed as the first recommended technique of intercultural teaching by endeavoring to do comparison and contrast between their own culture and the new one on the basis of theme and content [14], [15]. In the second option, students can be provided with concrete materials such as texts and documents, maps, pictures, diagrams, animation, or audio recordings during learning process. Teachers and students are expected to arrange in-depth discussions of the materials above. Textbook and visual learnings can be implemented as the third [16], [17]–[19]. Teachers are suggested to select textbooks written in another language to raise students' awareness of intercultural and critical perspectives [20], [21]. The most convenient method is probably the grammar learning where it can assist the learners to discuss cultural diversity and respect for human rights [7].

The vast difference between EFL and local language in ELT class can trigger various perspectives of the teachers. The definition of culture teaching can vary in distinct regions. The facilitative environment for ICC teaching is also deemed vital of any educational curriculum, Barrot *et al.* [22] states that expressing the crucial part of intercultural education is of importance in the education programs in Chinese, particularly within foreign language teaching circumstances. The majority of EFL teachers, however, considered that ICC is of paramount importance in teaching and learning process.

Intercultural teaching environment definitely depends on specific aspects influencing teachers' skills. Prior to presenting intercultural topic, teachers should be aware that language and culture cannot be separated from each other [23]. In real practice, however, it is considered difficult to integrate topic of target language and its relevant culture especially in early education. Providing that ICC is not innate to educators in non-English speaking countries, they ought not to be relied on solely knowledge and skills to be interculturally competent. Lee *et al.* [24] describe the aspects affecting teachers' intercultural teaching skills, namely: motivation or attitudes which involve feelings and perceptions impactful to one's readiness to embrace intercultural communication, prejudice towards other cultures which influence decisions and behaviors. These aspects are later used to assist in promoting ICC in the foreign language class.

Intercultural teaching skills or intercultural teaching competence (general English) has attained an immense notice from language scholars. It pinpoints to the ability of language educators "to interact with students in a way that supports the learning of students who are linguistically, culturally, socially, or in other ways diverse from the instructor or from each other" [25]. With high competence in intercultural teaching, teachers are able boost the learning process by building relationships with students [26]. ITC models are proposed by Dimitrov and Haque [27] which encompass three subsets of intercultural competencies, namely: i) foundational competence that covers the teacher's knowledge on their own positionality and ability to perceive the differences; ii) facilitation competencies concern on the capacity of teachers to compose a learning environment which is full of inclusiveness and safety, as well as on the dialogue promotion in the classroom; and iii) curriculum design competencies which incorporate an ability to enhance curriculum with various perspectives by trawling for contents, learning activities, assessments, and modelling.

Intercultural learning must be perceived sustainably as permeating cultures requires a range of time until actualization process. So far, no previous studies have identified the learning process of ICC in ESP setting, particularly in aviation context. Several studies only denote the learning process which is not longitudinal thus it is quite challenging to elaborate the concept of culture assimilation process between countries. Mede and Gunes [28] aim to point out the perceptions of students before and after integrating ICC in an elementary level English course, as well as the teacher's reflection by presenting the course regarding ICC use within English teaching. The research was administered to 20 EFL students and their teacher. It was discovered that there existed noticeable differences of them after involving ICC, that their awareness was significantly increased about their own culture and the role of culture during the learning process. Similar study was conducted by Batunan *et al.* [29] focusing on teachers' perceptions towards promoting ICC in the EFL classroom. The results serve implications for teachers' development and teaching and learning pedagogy as follows: ICC is difficult to define thus they should seek opportunities to enrich intercultural knowledge by joining courses or workshop. Some of them are lacking intercultural knowledge in the textbook, thus it is quite a conundrum to promote ICC. Role-play is primarily employed as it is deemed the most effective strategy. Therefore, enhancing ICC can be a showcase to promote both linguistic and ICC [24], [30]–[32].

As practically and theoretically, ongoing information regarding intercultural learning, including perception and learning practices of teachers, is still required, this study aims to describe the learning process of intercultural topic with ESP setting in aviation English class. It employs autobiographical method which later shall scrutinize teachers' practices in the early period of teaching until the end and relate it to the practice conducted by them. Detailed illustrations are therefore obtained from the thorough intercultural teaching process conducted by teachers. Hence, there would be the needs to re-assess ICC tools and instrument, regarding the awareness of the learners' and later to be applied to ESP syllabus design [33].

2. LITERATURE REVIEWS

2.1. Intercultural competence

Each individual must be able to compete globally and adjust to specific culture whenever required. One should be armed with the knowledge and skills to interact within cultural diversity, especially when it has turned into manifestation in global marketplace, causing it to be inevitably important. ICC primarily consists of five components, namely attitudes, knowledge, interpretation and relation skills, discovery and interaction skills, and critical cultural awareness [34], [35]. These models emphasize on the specific educational purposes addressed to language and culture learning and function as guidelines to develop and assess students' ICC in the foreign language learning process. The intercultural aspects which should be of the primary concern and developed by learners include awareness, attitudes, skills, and knowledge [36]. Furthermore, two notions above are transformed into pyramid model by Deardorff [37] whose immediate external output is as the consequence of intercultural acquisition, attitudes and/or attitudes and skills/knowledge. All three propositions henceforth come to mutual understanding regarding intercultural knowledge, attitudes, and skills, where two of which [38] have component in common, namely intercultural awareness.

Banjongjit and Boonmoh [39] remark that it is essential to observe the strategies to promote ICC within language class which encompasses cognitive, affective and behavioral components. Before delving into more in-depth comprehension, one should be aware of identifying their own culture and adapting to the distinct cultures. Byram [7] postulate four applicable techniques for teachers to promote ICC, namely: i) comparative analysis by suggesting students to do comparison and contrast between cultures on the basis of theme and content, e.g., role-play; ii) teachers can employ authentic materials, e.g., documents, maps, photographs, diagrams, cartoons, and audio recordings, by analyzing the origin of the publication. Students are encouraged to do discussion to measure their understanding; iii) textbooks written with an intercultural and critical perspective can be used as well. Teachers can employ the materials such as grammar exercises to widen students' views on different cultures; and iv) it is helpful to teach several new vocabularies which assists students to discuss cultural diversity, and encourage them to respect the rules of discussion as a part of a respect for human rights altogether. At the end of the day, when multicultural circumstances are encountered, students already have the broad, even detailed, comprehension towards the differences.

2.2. English for specific purposes: context of aviation English class with ICC

In this rapid growth of global development, one must be equipped with linguistic competence to integrate their interest with multicultural scope. Foreign languages have become a part of urgent matter to involve in such situation. English, which takes place at the top of lingua franca, is gauged to be a facilitative element for intercultural communication. Some matters, however, require specific sets of lexicons in particular circumstances called ESP. ESP is defined as a language learning approach on the basis of learner necessity [40], [41]. Then, what is the difference between ESP and general English (GE)? Teachers of the latter are not frequently encountered with their students' specific needs, while the former ones are specified to particular discourse, and teachers should adjust the courses syllabus to students' purposes [42].

It is not guaranteed that foreign language mastery which includes native-like skill will bring success in intercultural circumstances which involves group from heterogeneous linguistic and cultural background. It is expected that an effective English user does not only own language ability but also to go on with intercultural perspective including appropriate attitudes, empathy, and mutual understanding with the interlocutors [43]. This situation occurs in Aviation Polytechnic of Surabaya (Politeknik Penerbangan Surabaya) where cadets are not facilitated enough with ESP learning to broaden their cultural acquaintance, skill, and attitude. First, they are not administered with knowledge of multicultural environment, cultural knowledge and acculturation processes, intercultural communication and ICC acquisition. Second, the needs for local culture analysis are not covered in topical competence. Third, students' attitudes are not shaped to respect diverse cultures, tolerance and openness, and deal with psychological impedimenta and conundrums of ICC development (ethnocentrism, xenophobia, racism, ethnic prejudice). This inadequacy issues later become complication when the cadets are situated in the international workforce which necessitates ICC. In regard to it intercultural

competence instructional model (ICCIM) is prepared to assist the cadets for actual workplace where it should be developed on the basis of cadets' linguistic background.

3. METHOD

The present study used autobiographical study to explain the researcher's perceptions and practices in conducting ICC teaching in aviation English class [44]. The researcher also became the instrument in the present study as well as the subject due to the fact that the data were in the forms of experience and construct aspects such as knowledge. The researcher was an English lecturer at Politeknik Penerbangan Surabaya, Surabaya, Indonesia.

The polytechnic was one of official campuses under the Indonesian Ministry of Transportation where their graduates were mostly welcomed as civil servants, especially in aviation field. At last, Sigmund Freud's autobiographical [45] was used in the present study to explain every phenomenon, feeling, and emotion when conducting ICC teaching. In this study, the researcher aimed to explain the perceptions of teaching ICC in aviation English class including the importance of ICC for aviation English students, the expected learning goals and obstacles, along with the beliefs to carry out the teaching process.

In addition, the researcher also aimed to describe how the teaching and learning process was undertaken by focusing on portraying classroom situations, including students' physical attitudes, responses, and feelings. In coping with the practice of ICC teaching responses, the researcher also depicted some students' reflective journals that confirmed the researcher's teaching experience. Therefore, documentation of the reflective journals after the teaching and learning process was necessary.

The present study used ICCIM developed by the researcher adapting by Byram [46] and Joyce [47] ICC instructional theories. There were five major components namely syntax, social system, principles of reactions, support systems, and effects of the model. These five components of ICCIM would be permeated in three main learning activities to carry out the English learning objectives as well as the intercultural learning objectives. Figure 1 shows the ICCIM and Table 1 conveys the learning topics in aviation English class permeated with ICC materials.

Figure 1. Intercultural communicative competence based instructional model

Table 1. The blueprint of aviation English materials with ICC

Unit	English Materials	Learning Objectives	Learning Indicators
1	Conditional sentence	<p>English learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand conditional sentence types I, II, and III. <p>Intercultural learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand indigenous cultures in Indonesia, Thailand, and China (basic cultural). 	<p>English learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand conditional sentence type I. – Cadets understand conditional sentence type II. – Cadets understand conditional type III. <p>Intercultural learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand indigenous cultures in Indonesia. – Cadets understand indigenous cultures in Thailand. – Cadets understand indigenous cultures in China.
2	Compound and complex sentence	<p>English learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand compound and complex sentence. <p>Intercultural learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities and differences between Indonesian and Malaysian cultures (basic cultural). 	<p>English learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand compound sentence. – Cadets understand complex sentence. <p>Intercultural learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities between Indonesian and Malaysian cultures. – Cadets understand the differences between Indonesian and Malaysian cultures.
3	Gerund and infinitive	<p>English learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand gerund and infinitive. <p>Intercultural learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities and differences between Indonesian and Singaporean cultures (advanced cultural). 	<p>English learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand gerund. – Cadets understand infinitive. <p>Intercultural learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities between Indonesian and Singaporean cultures. – Cadets understand the differences between Indonesian and Singaporean cultures.
4	Weather (aviation English)	<p>English learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand some weathers including sunny, rainy, cloudy, and snow. <p>Intercultural learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities and differences between Indonesian and Japanese cultures due to different weathers (advanced cultural). 	<p>English learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand sunny weather. – Cadets understand rainy weather. – Cadets understand cloudy weather. – Cadets understand snowy weather. <p>Intercultural learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities between Indonesian and Japanese cultures due to different weathers. – Cadets understand the differences between Indonesian and Japanese cultures due to different weathers.
5	Aircraft (aviation English)	<p>English learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand different types of aircrafts. <p>Intercultural learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities and differences between Indonesian and Indian culinary offered in the aircraft (intercultural). 	<p>English learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand passenger aircraft. – Cadets understand cargo aircraft. <p>Intercultural learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the similarities between Indonesian and Indian culinary offered in the aircraft. – Cadets understand the differences between Indonesian and Indian culinary offered in the aircraft.
6	Airport (aviation English)	<p>English learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand parts of airport including terminal building, runway, and control tower. <p>Intercultural learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the different architectures between Indonesian and Malaysian airports (intercultural). 	<p>English learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand terminal building of airport. – Cadets understand runway of airport. – Cadets understand control tower of airport. <p>Intercultural learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand the architectures used in Soekarno-Hatta International Airport. – Cadets understand the architectures used in Kuala Lumpur International Airport.
7	Phraseology for aircraft maintenance engineers (aviation English)	<p>English learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand how to use some technical tools such as screwdriver and pincer <p>Intercultural learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand Indonesian and Singaporean cultures in term of conducting aircraft maintenance (intercultural). 	<p>English learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand how to use different types of screwdrivers. – Cadets understand how to use different types of pincers. <p>Intercultural learning indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cadets understand Indonesian cultures in term of conducting aircraft maintenance. – Cadets understand Singaporean culture in term of conducting aircraft maintenance.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Teacher's belief and practices towards the ICCIM for aviation English class

The teaching and learning process was divided into three main activities namely pre-learning, whilst-learning, and post-learning. In the pre-learning activities, the teacher, the author of this study, gave the visualization/text to stimulate students' schemata. The teacher could give several inducement questions to activate their schemata. If they had no ideas, they were requested to guess from what country the cultures were originated. They might analyze the given visualization/text closely. After, the teacher gave a brief explanation related to the pictures/visualization and asked the students what if their current lives experienced such a culture. At the final stage of this pre-learning activities, the teacher explained the English materials learned and showed how the class would be carried out. Generally, there were three tasks that should be accomplished in the class undertaken by the teacher. First, the teacher exposed to the English learning materials such as language building. Second, the teacher exposed to some cultures that would be discussed. Third, the teacher asked the students' schemata about the cultures discussed and asked them to imagine if they became the target culture members.

In sequence, the whilst-learning activities should be carried out more detailed. The teacher started to explain the grammar of the course (regarding the English learning objectives for each unit). Then, the teacher gave examples of the sentences using the learned grammar and exposed to some specific vocabularies related to the cultures depicted in the previously given visualization/text. The teacher confirmed students' understanding of the given examples. Classically, the teacher asked the students to take another example and write the sentences. Afterward, the teacher asked the students to make an oral presentation about Why does such a culture happen? What if you get that culture? What will you do?, and, Why does your reason justifiable? After delivering the topics presented, the teacher gave the students 10 minutes to prepare the answers using the English grammar learned. The teacher gave each student 5 minutes to present the answer in front of the class. Then, the teacher gave leading questions about the differences between the introduced cultures with their background cultures: what the introduced cultures had and what their background cultures had. Moreover, the teacher led the students to understand different cultural identities. Here, the teacher might conduct a discussion, either individually or in a group. Besides, the teacher also gave feedback to improve the students' English skills. In this whilst-learning activities, the main tasks encompassed answering questions related to English materials, making essays/presentations as the further student assignments by permeating the discussed cultural knowledge, identifying the similarities and differences of the discussed cultures, and discussing the results with the group members or between groups.

At the final stage of the teaching and learning process, the teacher should carry out the post-learning activities by the aims of recalling what had been learned and implicating to self-reflections. At first, the teacher could confirm students' understanding of the learned grammar for the pre-intermediate English course. At the same time, the teacher confirmed students' understanding of the learned cultures. The teacher emphasized that the learned cultures were diverse and not objective and showed the fact that the introduced cultures were ideologically constructed differently. The teacher asked the students to write a reflective journal pointing out their understanding, what they felt about the grammar materials, what they felt about the cultures, what they knew and did not know, and what they expected to get further. Then, the lecturer explained the next materials and ended the class. Here, there were three main tasks that should be accomplished namely discussing the possible English learning obstacles, imagining if they become the members of the discussed cultures, and writing a short journal to reflect their understanding of the English materials as well as the experience of learning about cultures. Before coping with the three stages of learning activities, the researcher found that designing ICC teaching especially in being permeated in aviation English course got so many obstacles. The researcher had problems in breaking down the course syllabus and put intercultural materials into it. The course syllabus only covered GE materials such as basic grammars and aviation English such as aircraft and airport. The researcher decided to bring some Asian cultures such as from Malaysia, Thailand, Japan, Singapore, and Chinese due to the fact that Indonesia's diverse cultures had almost shared similarities with theirs. The researcher believed that, as the beginning of teaching ICC, it was better to bring something in commons where students' schemata was almost there. Consequently, as the teacher, the researcher needed to stimulate similarities between Indonesia's cultures and the aforementioned countries' cultures. The researcher tried to make a small talk in the pre-learning activities by comparing pictures or videos portraying almost similar cultures but from different countries. Another rationale of this consideration was the fact that bearing a force of tolerance and understanding was essential when learning cultures [48], [49]. Therefore, the researcher brought the Asian cultures into the lesson.

When deciding the learning objectives, the researcher had difficulties in making chronological learning objectives without separating English learning objectives and ICC learning objectives. However, this was too difficult so the researcher was only able to make separation between English learning objectives and intercultural learning objectives. It was almost difficult without separation in terms of providing relevant assessment instruments. By this separation of the two types of learning objectives, the researcher could assess

the English materials with appropriate instrumentation and so do the intercultural materials. During this stage, the researcher tried to define three levels of ICC into seven units of English materials (see Table 1), covering basic cultural, advanced cultural, and intercultural. Basic cultural referred to the basic mastery of ICC consisting of understanding of other cultures and advanced cultural referred to the upper mastery where students could differentiate the cultures [50]. The intercultural level was the higher of ICC level where students could put themselves into the target cultures [51], [52]. By accomplishing these levels, the ICC mastery would be easily supervised and tracked the progression.

Another challenge in the preparation stage, the researcher found some crucial factors in learning process namely the media and the community/environment supports. Teaching ICC was new to the teaching environment in Politeknik Penerbangan Surabaya, where most teachers taught about basic knowledge of compulsory courses such as aviation English and other knowledge about aviation. This consequently affected the researcher's preparation in providing good learning media that could accommodate both English and ICC materials in the same time. Due to the very limited resources and, to the best of the researcher's knowledge and experience, it had been no appropriate learning media accommodating both materials especially integrated with aviation English exposures. This made the researcher step another stage namely preparing and developing appropriate module. This module was developed based on the ICCIM and the learning objectives portrayed in Table 1 with the expert validators consisting of one local lecturer whose expertise was in aviation English as well as basic aviation knowledge. The other validators were the lecturers of ICC in Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, who became the researcher's partners in constructing the present study. After following the steps of analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation (ADDIE) model in developing the module, the researcher started to trialed the module before use in a small group discussion section to gather more information including the fits of the materials and learning targets. At last, the researcher had the appropriate media, which was only reliable and valid to the context of aviation English carried out in Politeknik Penerbangan Surabaya.

In coping with the community supports, the researcher found that the community was not ready to permeate ICC in their teaching procedures. This was due to the fact that few of the community members covering instructors and lecturers/teachers were exposed to ICC teaching. Even ICC teaching was indeed important to the researcher's perceptions, supported by the presence of some previous theories and studies [53], [54], the teaching habit was extraneous to the idea of ICC. This situation made the researcher work by himself to accommodate the cadets needs in learning ICC. By this case, the researcher believed that the lacks of ICC knowledge perceived by other teachers and their reluctance in providing ICC-based instruction showed that the researcher's colleagues' self-efficacy in teaching ICC was low. They almost had no eagerness to learn the ICCIM, for instance, to take up space the needs of learning other countries' cultures. Moreover, this reflected that the communal self-efficacy in teaching ICC was absolutely low since the teaching environment did not apprehend it, such as in [55]. This fact made the researcher more exhausted in preparing the ICC teaching in aviation English but still felt challenging, highly motivated, and extremely confident.

4.2. Students' knowledge, attitude and practice towards the ICCIM for aviation English class

This study described how the researcher conducted the pre-, whilst-, and post-learning activities. The description portrayed in the study was only the majority that happened in each learning stage. Details were included once it was unique to be discussed or appeared in certain case only. Figure 2 shows the order of the teacher's teaching activities in the pre-learning stage.

Figure 2. Pre-learning activities of ICC teaching in aviation English

In the pre-learning activities, there were five steps in introducing the ICC and aviation English materials. In the first step, the teacher, the researcher himself, stimulated students' cultural schemata by providing pictures or videos revealing the Asian cultures. When the researcher showed the pictures, the students' face turned to be curious and happy because they were challenged to guess where the cultures were originated. Some of them said correct guess and some others were laughing because they were unsure where they were originated. Here, the researcher found that this step was indeed meaningful in activating their schemata and eagerness in participating the whole learning process. The researcher found more interesting phenomena when the students were asked to tell the reasons of their guess answers. They used several clues or features in the pictures or videos to explain their characteristics and involvement in certain cultures. For example, they might see a batik fabric as from Indonesia and not belong to Japanese cultures. This step activated their analysis skills a lot which was relevant to the practice of the 21st-century education [56]. After having intense and interesting discussion, the research led the students to listen to the explanation where the cultures portrayed in the pictures or videos were originated. When they were asked the feelings of having similar cultures with other countries, the students firstly could not accept it. This might be due to the fact that they were still in the very low of basic cultural awareness.

In addition, during the step of asking students' feelings, the researcher mostly found that some critical students showed important arguments. For instance, a student conveyed that Indonesian and Malaysian cultures almost shared similarities since they were neighborhood with similar characteristics. He showed the similarities of the language, the tribes, and some foods. This analysis was interesting because he could accept the fact of similarities. However, other students were still curious how to differentiate the Indonesian and Malaysian cultures. This phenomenon was also unique because, instead of appropriating similarities, they still wanted to recognize the cultural identities that made different. The researcher assumed that this feeling was a reflection of nationality where they wanted to protect the cultures and to promote exclusivism in cultures [57]. This was not able to be judged as wrong conception because the students were still on the process of appropriating other countries' cultures, or called negotiation process. In this step, the researcher also realized that, as cultures were parts of country's identity, perceiving identity was formed in three different ways namely appropriation, negotiation, and resistance. Therefore, the feeling of half-appropriation and half-resistance was normal to negotiate cultural values.

In coping with the delivery of English material introduction, the researcher had no significant problems as this was commonly undertaken when teaching English. The students responded some introductory English materials very well because they knew the core of the topic covered on aviation English. However, the students' responses were not even better than when responding the ICC material introduction. The researcher found that this was interesting since the students experienced the ICC teaching in the first time. Referring to above chronological pre-learning activities along with the researchers' findings, the researcher believed that ICC teaching was a kind of interesting topic that could be accepted and applied regardless the classroom situation.

Some previous research explained that pre-learning activities were crucial in generating students' learning motivation [58], [59]. Some students might not be motivated to learn since their schemata was not yet activated and they had been prepared psychologically to learn certain materials [60], [61]. Meşe and Sevilen [62] stated that psychological readiness should be considered important in succeeding the transfer knowledge and achieving the expected learning goal. Moreover, Schnitzler *et al.* [63] found that uninteresting pre-learning activities led students to low learning self-efficacy so intention and confident to accomplish the learning process was absent. The activation of good learning psychology could be carried out by having small talks and recalling some relevant materials in order to engage with the upcoming materials learned [63]. The use of several media such as pictures and videos could assist the occurrence of small talks and brainstorming process, like what the researcher had exemplified. Another case was the fact that teaching new things like ICC in the English classroom activities provided more authentic materials where student could relate the cultures of different countries, even they were no need to travel into other countries. This experience of ICC introduction in the stage of pre-learning activities was absolutely crucial [64]. Figure 3 illustrates while-learning tasks of ICC teaching in aviation English. This comprises four distinct phases, namely: answering questions related to English materials, making essays/presentations as the further student assignments by permeating the discussed cultural knowledge, identifying the similarities and differences of the discussed cultures, discussing the results with the group members or between groups.

In the case of whilst-learning activities, the researcher did some difficult mixture of learning activities. The researcher should explain the English learning materials but in the same time engaging the ICC materials. It was indeed overlapping materials and was difficult to be undertaken. However, using the chronological steps in the whilst-learning activities could help lead the research teach both ICC and English materials. The researcher had no significant problems in following the chronological learning process in this stage. Unfortunately, the researcher found that the whilst-learning activities tasks found some obstacles to be accomplished by the students. First, in answering questions related to English materials, the researcher found

some confusion in the students' face when they had to talk about two different things, e.g., ICC and English materials. Consequently, the research tried to restate the claim that ICC materials were the materials used as context when learning grammar materials. For instance, in unit 1, the students learned about conditional sentence as the English materials and understood about Indonesian, Thailand, and Chinese indigenous cultures. The examples of conditional sentence used the context of the target cultures. The sentence could ask the students to imagine how if they became parts of the target cultures. This explanation further gave insights how the students should tackle the first tasks in differentiating ICC and English materials.

Figure 3. Whilst-learning tasks of ICC teaching in aviation English

When the researcher asked the students to make a presentation about the English material topic with the injection of ICC knowledge, the students were interested in exploring to understand the target cultures (i.e., Indonesian, Thailand, and Chinese cultures). They were courageous to explore the differences and similarities of the target cultures. The researcher assumed that the students started to appropriate the ICCIM so they had already known how to handle the ICC teaching permeated in aviation English class. In coping with the results of the presentation product, coming to the last tasks as well, the researcher discussed the differences and similarities of the target cultures classically with the students. This task was used as a confirmatory stage to ensure whether all students had understood the cultural materials. Question-answer session was supported to elicit some misunderstanding and to strengthen students' ICC. At last, the researcher believed that the practice of ICCIM in the whilst-learning activities had successfully led the students to explore more ICC materials.

Exploration and experience more cultures during the whilst-learning activities were necessary in bridging different ICC levels [24]. For instance, basic cultural awareness should be done by portraying more characteristics of the target culture rather than generating more critical thinking of finding uniqueness and distinctions [65]–[67]. In regard to advanced cultural competence, the students' whilst-learning activities should accommodate the culture's characteristics in one aspect, such as being portrayed in unit 4. In unit 4, the researcher asked the students to differentiate between Indonesian and Japanese cultures based on different weathers. This led the absorption of better cultural comprehension so the students could perceive more detailed ICC. At last, in the ICC level, the researcher gave students opportunity to experience or to put themselves within the cultures so they could appropriate the cultures and understand why the target cultures were designed and existing differently. These three different exploratory activities might create step-by-step assistance in learning ICC. Figure 4 emphasizes the subsequent tasks involved in teaching aviation English using the ICC approach. These tasks can be divided into two distinct steps: engaging in a dialogue about the acquired knowledge and verifying students' comprehension and composing a concise logbooks entry to contemplate their comprehension of the English contents, as well as their experience of acquiring knowledge about different cultures.

In the post-learning activities, the researcher concentrated on the students' understanding of English materials and their experience in learning ICC. In connection with the students' English mastery, the researcher asked the researcher whether they had additional questions about the materials. The students mostly did not raise new questions, rather, they only confirmed whether their understanding about the materials was correct. To ensure their correct conception, the researcher tried to aurally test the students in random order. The aural test consisting of recapping the English materials learned along with the examples using the ICC context. The

researcher also gave some home tasks in connection with the learned materials to strengthen their understanding. In coping with the ICC materials, the researcher asked the students to make a reflective journal pointing out their ICC learning experience in aviation English class. Some students said that they were more interested in learning ICC because they got new cultural perspectives and knowledge. They felt happy during the learning process because the media was interesting and recapped the needs to learn cultures. They always put higher eagerness when they learned the upcoming ICC materials. Some students also conveyed that it was challenging to understand different cultures with limited clues as they were not exposed to the cultures previously. This condition implied that the students accepted the ICCIM applied in the aviation English class.

Figure 4. Post-learning tasks of ICC teaching in aviation English

Unfortunately, what the researcher experienced during the ICC learning in aviation English class was probably relevant to the class where the researcher conducted. The responses to the ICCIM and ICC materials could be greatly diverse due to dissimilar student and school characteristics [68], [69]. Moreover, the Asian cultures brought in the present study were chosen based on the availability of differences and similarities to Indonesian cultures, thus, not all Asian cultures were introduced. The practice of ICC learning conveyed by the researcher was also limited since there was a need to adapt the ICC materials with the aviation English materials. Consequently, the ICC materials still needed to be more exposed with diverse cultural experience, practices, and information. Therefore, this autobiographical study needed to be supported by further research in wider limitations with wider cultural scopes.

5. CONCLUSION

ICC teaching should be well prepared where ICCIM introduced in the present study can be used as guidance for teachers. The study still believe that ICC teaching should be carried out especially when students will work in a multicultural context such as in aviation field. This ICC teaching lets students understand other cultures; therefore, they can determine their attitudes when practically interacting with other cultures. This autobiographical study describes how the ICCIM can be implemented in aviation English class with three learning stages namely pre-, whilst-, and post-learning activities. The study also depicts students' feelings and experience during the ICC learning process in which most of them are interested on learning it. Our findings provide conclusive evidence which recommends ICCIM and ICC teaching plan for aviation English learning.

This research had implications both practically and theoretically. Practically, this research could help English lecturers practice their intercultural teaching using the intercultural-based English instructional model in the English classroom. It invited the lecturers to consider not only the rules of English but also the cultural content in the organization of their materials. Besides, it also suggested the lecturers provide an equal proportion of time for promoting English and ICC. Theoretically, this study provided information to English lecturers about the intercultural-based English instructional model and the processes of intercultural-based English learning in the classroom. It informed them of the stages as well as the benefits and costs that they might face during the teaching and learning activities. It also provided useful references for further research for other scholars. As suggestion, this autobiographical study can be the basis of generating more quantitative research in determining the effectiveness of ICCIM and the students' mastery of ICC. Moreover, future research can use diverse cultures included in the learning process so the results can be justified by different cultural contents.

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